

ANTENATAL CARE PRACTICES ADOPTED BY RURAL PREGNANT WOMEN AND THEIR FAMILIES IN PARBHANI DISTRICT

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Abstract

A sample of 150 rural pregnant women belonging to middle and low SES groups residing in 5 villages of Parbhani district were selected by adopting purposive random sampling method. The data pertaining to the study were collected by personally interviewing the sample rural pregnant women based on open ended interview schedule. Irrespective of Socio-economic status, it was observed that a higher percentage of rural pregnant women (88-91%) did their ANC registration during their first trimester of pregnancy. A higher percentage of them (54.66%) did it at private hospital followed by at Civil hospital and Primary health centre (18.66%) and in rural hospital (8.00%). Irrespective of SES all the rural pregnant women's weight, height, Hb level, blood pressure were assessed and urine, blood, VDRL and HIV test and pelvic tests were done. Further it was found that a higher percentage of them (88-98%) were also undergone ultrasonography. In addition to these, all the sample rural pregnant women were found to have taken TT vaccination as well as IFA tablets, followed by calcium and multivitamin tablets (97-100%). The results of this study proved that during pregnancy for positive outcome, pregnant women avoided lifting heavy weight, wore comfortable footwear to avoid accidents, wore comfortable clothes and also avoided journey for avoiding complications during pregnancy. In addition to these, it was observed that rural pregnant women's families also taken special care of them for the best outcome of pregnancy.

Keywords: Antenatal care, Pregnancy, Early registration, Prenatal, Awareness, Utilization of ANC services

Introduction

Antenatal care (ANC) is the health care provided to women who are pregnant, for confirmation and monitoring of the progress of their pregnancy, and to promote their birth preparedness and complication readiness for ensuring optimal birth outcomes for both the mother and her baby (WHO, 2016). ANC service from its initiation in the ancient times has been a part of preventive medicine. In which the attempts were made to ensure the safety of the mother and the child by focusing more on some major aspects like screening, follow up, advice and intervention avoiding pregnancy related complications. Antenatal care also play a critical role in preparing a woman and her family for birth by establishing confidence between the woman and her health care provider and by individualizing promotional health messages. Further antenatal visits raise awareness about the need for care during delivery or give women and their families a familiarity with health facilities that enables them to seek help more efficiently during a crisis. However, uptake of these services is far from universal even in settings where they are widely available. (Chandhiok et al., 2006).

Traditionally in rural India, pregnancy is considered as a natural state for a woman rather than a condition requiring medical attention and care. Even if antenatal visits are done, those are given less frequently and that too late in pregnancy. Besides these, it appears that antenatal services are utilized by women who experience difficulty or signals of a complicated delivery. Latest research has shown a lower still birth rate, among women with a minimum of 8 antenatal visits, based on which the minimum recommended number of antenatal contacts has now been increased from 4 to 8 (WHO, 2019). Quality antenatal, intranatal, and postnatal care is the single most important determinant of infants' as well as mothers' morbidity and mortality. The inequality in the health and well-being of women in the developing world is a cause of immense concern. Despite an array of national programs since independence for improving the health of the child as well as the mother, inadequate access and underutilization of modern health services are among the prime reasons for the high maternal mortality rate in India. Other common reasons include high illiteracy among females, early marriages, ignorance, low quality as well as high cost of service, social structure, detrimental health beliefs, personal characteristics, and malnutrition, especially among the rural and tribal populations. So, utilization of these services by the beneficiaries remains unsatisfactory. In the rural areas of India, ANMs are responsible for providing antenatal care, but the access and utilization of these

services is a matter of debate. (Ali and Chauhan, 2021). Therefore by considering above facts, it is felt necessary to study antenatal care practices adopted by rural families and general health problems encountered by the rural pregnant women during pregnancy.

Materials and Method

Total 150 rural women who are pregnant during the time of the study residing in 5 villages of Parbhani district of Marathwada region of Maharashtra State were selected to conduct this research study as the investigator was having easy approach to them. After obtaining consent from the rural pregnant women, the data pertaining to the study were collected by personally interviewing them based on structured and open ended interview schedule. Besides it, Kuppuswamy's socio-economic status (SES) scale revised by Dr. Sheikh Mohd. Saleem (2018) was administered on them for assessing their SES. Data collected from the rural pregnant women were pooled, tabulated, statistically analysed and discussed.

Results and Discussion

Table 1 reveals about antenatal care practices adopted by rural pregnant women. About 91.66 percent middle SES rural pregnant women and 88.88 percent low SES rural pregnant women reported that they did their ANC registration during their first trimester of pregnancy. Whereas a meagre percentage of them (8.00%) did it in second trimester and even in third trimester (02.22% low SES pregnant women). With reference to the place of ANC registration, it was observed that irrespective of SES, a higher percentage of them (54.66%) did it at private hospital followed by at Civil hospital and Primary health centre (18.66%) and in rural hospital (8.00%). When the sample rural pregnant women were enquired about the persons accompanied with them while going for ANC checkups, irrespective of SES a higher percentage of their husbands (62.00%) only accompanied with them followed by mother in laws (28.66%), mothers (6.00%) and sister in laws (4.00%). After registering for ANC services, it was observed that majority of them were the beneficiaries of Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana, Janani Suraksha Yojana under National Rural Health Mission as well as Integrated Child Development Services Scheme, Ministry of Women and Child Development Scheme, Govt. of India. Even though minimum 4 ANC visits are recommended by National Health Mission, Ministry of Health & Family Welfare, India. (2022), about 51.00 percent low SES rural pregnant women and 38.88 middle SES rural pregnant women were found to have given 1-3 ANC visits, followed by giving 4-6 (37-46%) and also more than six visits (11-15%). Some of the findings are in support of some of the results observed by Singh et al. (2012),

Roy et al. (2013), Gupta et al. (2015), Poona et al.(2017), and Jain et al. (2020).

Details about the ANC rural pregnant women undergone are given in Table 2. It is obvious from the results that as all the sample rural pregnant women were beneficiaries of various government Schemes like Pradhan Mantri Matru Vandana Yojana Scheme(PMMVY),Janani Surakha Yojana (JSY) and Integrated Child Development Services (ICDS) Schemes, irrespective of SES all the rural pregnant women's weight, height ,Hb level, blood pressure were assessed and urine, blood, VDRL and HIV test and pelvic tests were done. Further it was found that a higher percentage of them (88-98%) were also undergone ultrasonography. As all the sample rural pregnant women had done ANC registration, they were found to had taken TT vaccination as well as IFA tablets, followed by calcium and multivitamin tablets (97-100%).Except for undergoing ultrasonography, no significant differences were recorded among these rural pregnant women with respect to undergoing ANC checkups. These results are in line with the findings reported by Metgud et al. (2009) , Vidler et al. (2016) and Das et al. (2018) .

Information about special care taken by rural pregnant women for positive outcome were illustrated in the Table 3 and Fig 1. The results of this study proved that during pregnancy for positive outcome, pregnant women avoided lifting heavy weight, wore comfortable footwear to avoid accidents, wore comfortable clothes and also avoided journey for avoiding complications during pregnancy. The corresponding percentages of their counterparts low SES rural pregnant women were 100.00, 96.66, 90.00 and 72.22.Besides these, irrespective of SES, about 34 - 42 percent of them expressed that, they also avoided polluted environment and exposure to the diseases for avoiding health issues during pregnancy.

Table 4 and Fig 2 reveals the information about special care of rural pregnant women taken in their family. Regardless of SES, it was observed that more than 70.00 percent of rural pregnant women's families provided nutritious diet (70.00%), reduced heavy work load of the pregnant women (74.00%) allowed them to take enough rest during day time, sought guidance by the female family members about pregnancy care (82.00% each), restricted to go to market (96.00%) and to go out specially during night (98.66%). In addition to these, relatively a higher percentage of them found to made financial arrangement in advance for delivery and few of them also prepared clothes for new born (20.00%). By and large statistical

results prove that based on SES except for providing nutritious diet to pregnant women and keeping ready clothes for newborns, no significant differences were noticed among rural pregnant women's families while proving special care to them during pregnancy.

Efforts taken by the family members for mental well being of rural pregnant women during pregnancy are exhibited in Table 5 and Fig 3. Relatively a higher percentage of middle SES families provided moral support to the pregnant women for their mental well-being followed by helped in reducing mental stress (50.00%), arranged special programmes to celebrate pregnancy which is popular as choli programme/ Dohal Jevan (41.00%) and tried for keeping happy surroundings (40.00%). The corresponding percentages of their counterparts low SES rural pregnant women were observed to be 71.11, 44.44, 26.66 and 27.77. Overall statistically no significant differences were recorded among rural families with reference to the efforts taken by them for the mental wellbeing of rural pregnant women.

Conclusion

Irrespective of Socio- economic status, it was observed that a higher percentage of rural pregnant women (88-91%) did their ANC registration during their first trimester of pregnancy. A higher percentage of them (54.66%) did it at private hospital followed by at Civil hospital and Primary health centre (18.66%) and in rural hospital (8.00%). Irrespective of SES all the rural pregnant women's weight, height ,Hb level, blood pressure were assessed and urine, blood, VDRL and HIV test and pelvic tests were done. Further it was found that a higher percentage of them (88-98%) were also undergone ultrasonography. In addition to these, all the sample rural pregnant women were found to had taken TT vaccination as well as IFA tablets, followed by calcium and multivitamin tablets (97-100%). The results of this study proved that during pregnancy for positive outcome, pregnant women avoided lifting heavy weight, wore comfortable footwear to avoid accidents, wore comfortable clothes and also avoided journey for avoiding complications during pregnancy. In addition to these, it was observed that rural pregnant women's families also had taken special care of them for the best outcome of pregnancy.

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Table 1. Antenatal care practices adopted by rural pregnant women

Antenatal care practices adopted by rural pregnant women	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status (n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES (n=150)	Z values
ANC Registration				
In first trimester	88.88(80)	91.66(55)	90.00(135)	00.59 ^{NS}
In second trimester	08.88(08)	08.33(05)	08.66(13)	---
In third trimester	02.22(02)	---	01.33(02)	---
Places of ANC registration				
Private Hospital	52.22(47)	58.33(35)	54.66(82)	00.72 ^{NS}
Civil Hospital	18.88(17)	18.33(11)	18.66(28)	---
PHC	21.11(19)	15.00(09)	18.66(28)	00.95 ^{NS}
Rural Hospital	07.77(07)	08.33(05)	08.00(12)	00.22 ^{NS}
Accompanying person to ANC				
Husband	56.66(51)	68.33(42)	62.00(93)	01.50 ^{NS}
Mother in law	28.88(26)	28.33(17)	28.66(43)	---
Mother	10.00(09)	-	06.00(09)	---
Sister in law	04.44(04)	08.33(02)	04.00(06)	00.98 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies *P< 0.05 level **P < 0.01 level NS- Non Significant

Table 2 Details about the Antenatal check-ups rural pregnant women undergone

ANC rural women undergone	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status(n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES(n=150)	Z values
Weight	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Height	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Hb level	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Blood pressure	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Tests (VDRL,HIV)	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Urine	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Blood	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Pelvic test	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Ultra sonography	88.88(80)	98.33(59)	92.66(139)	02.58**
TT injections taken	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
IFA tablets taken	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Calcium and multivitamin tablets taken	97.77(88)	100(60)	98.66(148)	01.66 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies, *P< 0.05 level **P < 0.01 level NS- Non Significant

Table 3. Information about special care taken by rural pregnant women for positive outcome

Special care taken by pregnant women	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status(n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES(n=150)	Z values
Avoided lifting heavy weight	96.66(87)	100(60)	98.00(147)	00.19 ^{NS}
Wore comfortable footwear	100(90)	100(60)	100(150)	---
Wore more comfortable clothes	90.00(81)	100(60)	94.00(141)	03.16**
Avoided journey	72.22(65)	78.33 (47)	74.66(112)	00.84 ^{NS}
Avoided polluted environment	31.66(19)	48.88(44)	42.00(63)	02.13*
Avoided exposure to diseases	37.77(34)	30.00(18)	34.66(52)	00.89 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies, *P< 0.05 level **P < 0.01 level NS- Non Significant

Table 4 Information about special care of rural pregnant women taken in their family

Special care taken by pregnant women family members	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status (n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES(n=150)	Z values
Restricted to go out specially during night	97.77(88)	100 (60)	98.66(148)	01.66 ^{NS}
Restricted eating certain foods	96.66(87)	100(60)	98.00(147)	01.93 ^{NS}
Restricted to go in market	95.555(86)	96.66(58)	96.00(144)	00.29 ^{NS}
Guidance by female family members about pregnancy care	78.88(71)	86.66(52)	82.00(123)	01.27 ^{NS}
Allowed to take enough rest during day time	78.88(71)	86.66(52)	82.00(123)	01.27 ^{NS}
Reduced heavy work load	73.33(66)	75.00(45)	74.00(111)	00.27 ^{NS}
Provided nutritious diet	63.00(57)	80.00(48)	70.00(105)	02.34*
Preparations made for delivery				
Financial arrangement	56.66(51)	68.33(42)	62.00(13)	01.50 ^{NS}
Prepared clothes for new born	12.22(11)	31.66(19)	20.00(30)	02.76**

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies

*P< 0.05 level **P < 0.01 level NS- Non Significant

Tables 5: Efforts taken by the family members for mental well-being of rural pregnant women during pregnancy

Efforts taken by pregnant women and family members for mental well-being during pregnancy	Percentage of rural pregnant women based on socio-economic status (n=150)			
	Low SES (n=90)	Middle SES (n=60)	Percentage of rural pregnant women irrespective of SES(n=150)	Z values
Provided moral supports	71.11(64)	78.33(47)	74.00(111)	00.97 ^{NS}
Helped in reduced mental stress	44.44(40)	50.00(30)	46.66(70)	00.72 ^{NS}
Arranged special programmes to celebrate pregnancy (Choli, Dohal jevan)	26.66(24)	41.66(25)	32.66(49)	01.90 ^{NS}
Tried for keeping happy surrounding	27.77(25)	40.00(24)	32.66(49)	01.65 ^{NS}

Figures in parenthesis indicate frequencies, NS- Non Significant

Fig 1: Information about special care taken by the rural pregnant women for positive outcome

Fig 2: Information about special care taken by the rural pregnant women's family members for positive outcome

Fig 3: : Efforts taken by the family members for mental well-being of rural pregnant women during pregnancy

References

1. Ali, B., and Chauhan, S.(2020) Inequalities in the utilisation of maternal health Care in Rural India: Evidences from National Family Health Survey III & IV. *BMC Public Health* 20, 369 . <https://doi.org/10.1186/s12889-020-08480-4>
2. Chandhiok, N., Dhillon, B. S., Kambo, I., and Saxena, N. C. (2006). Determinants of antenatal care utilization in rural areas of India: A cross-sectional study from 28 districts (An ICMR task force study). *J Obstet Gynecol India*, 56(1), 47-52.
3. Das, B. N., Kanakamedala, S., and Mummadi, M. K. (2018). Factors associated with utilization of antenatal care services among rural women, Telangana, India. *Int J Commun Med Public Health*, 5(7), 1.
4. Jain, P., and Jain, V. Knowledge and practices regarding antenatal care among pregnant females visiting antenatal clinic at tertiary care hospital in Delhi. *Education*, 31(40yrs), 86.
5. Metgud, C. S., Katti, S. M., Mallapur, M. D., and Wantamutte, A. S. (2009). Utilization patterns of antenatal services among pregnant women: a longitudinal study in rural area of north Karnataka. *Al Ameen J Med Sci*, 2(1), 58-62.
6. Ponna, S. N., Upadrasta, V. P., Geddani, J. B., Dudala, S. R., Sadasivuni, R., and Bathina, H. (2017). Regional variation in utilization of Antenatal care services in the state of Andhra Pradesh. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, 6(2), 231.

7. **Gupta, R. K., Shora, T. N., Verma, A. K., & Jan, R. (2015).** Knowledge regarding antenatal care services, its utilization, and delivery practices in mothers (aged 15-49 years) in a rural area of North India. *Trop J Med Res*, 18(2), 89-94.
8. **Roy, M. P., Mohan, U., Singh, S. K., Singh, V. K., and Srivastava, A. K. (2013).** Determinants of utilization of antenatal care services in rural Lucknow, India. *Journal of family medicine and primary care*, 2(1), 55.
9. **Singh, P. K., Rai, R. K., Alagarajan, M., and Singh, L. (2012).** Determinants of maternity care services utilization among married adolescents in rural India. *PLoS one*, 7(2), e31666.
10. **Vidler, M., Ramadurg, U., Charantimath, U., Katageri, G., Karadiguddi, C., Sawchuck, D., ... and Mallapur, A. (2016).** Utilization of maternal health care
11. **World Health Organization. WHO** recommendations on antenatal care for a positive pregnancy experience. World Health Organization; 2016. Accesed., <https://apps.who.int/iris/bits...>
12. **WHO (2019)**WHO recommendations on antenatal care for a positive pregnancy experience.WHO. http://www.who.int/reproductivehealth/publications/maternal_perinatal_health/anc-positive-pregnancy-experience/en/].